

**Lived Experiences of the Grade 7 English Language
Teachers on the MATATAG Curriculum Implementation at
the Division of Bataan: A Development Plan**

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Abstract

This research explored the lived experiences of the Grade 7 Junior High School English language teachers in implementing the MATATAG Curriculum at the Schools Division of Bataan S.Y. 2024-2025, which is the basis for the development plan. Interviews and focus group discussions (FGD) were utilized to collect qualitative data, which was analyzed through thematic analysis. Based on the findings, the MATATAG curriculum cited obstacles among language teachers, such as insufficient resources, complicated demands, and the burden of overwork among teachers. These problems pointed to the importance of support, provision of readymade resources, and adjustment to the scope of the new curriculum. Without these solutions, the goals and objectives of the MATATAG Curriculum will be challenging to realize. Moreover, the crafted development plan provided approaches to solving the gaps and challenges faced by the teachers. It includes teacher professional development, resource optimization, curriculum adaptation, peer collaboration, teacher well-being, and student support.

Keywords:

English Language Teachers, Lived Experiences, Junior High School, MATATAG Curriculum, Qualitative,

Introduction

English language teachers' experiences in implementing new curricula pose them with challenges that condition their practices. Some common obstacles include large classes, limited instructional time, poor facilities, limited training, and challenges in meeting standards (Nguyen et al., 2024; Pak et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2024). Another challenges English teachers face in implementing new curriculum are cultural and social challenges (Huang, 2021; Lou, 2017), inadequate technology and resources (Yulianti, 2023; Sarikhani et al., 2020), and issues of cooperating with parents (Imran et al., 2024). Such challenges are addressed with an array of technical and adaptive controls alongside the patronage of varied stakeholders like instructors, administrators, and policymakers (Pak et al., 2020; Liang, 2021).

The implementation of the MATATAG curriculum by English language teachers in the Philippines is a colossal shift in educational methodology, addressing the issues encountered by the current K to-12 system (Estrallado, 2023). "MATATAG" is the term used in the curriculum that denotes resilience, where its primary objective is to improve literacy and numeracy skills and socio-emotional development as the foundational skills needed for lifelong learning (Magsampol, 2024).

The MATATAG Curriculum's pilot implementation has brought opportunities and challenges to the English language teachers for the junior high school. According to Estrallado (2023), implementing a new curriculum is necessary to improve education quality and keep up with the needs of society. However, Sigales (2024) noted that even though the MATATAG curriculum presents a framework that aims to develop the students' foundational skills, its implementation negatively affects the teachers by increasing workloads, stress, and exhaustion. Magsampol (2024) reported that language teachers complained about the chaotic rollout of the new curriculum, particularly about

its added programs, like the National Reading Program (NRP), that doubled their workload for additional preparation.

While the MATATAG curriculum is a good step toward addressing educational challenges in the Philippines, effective implementation will be dependent upon adequate teacher training and support (Bentayao et al., 2024; Saro et al., 2024). English language teaching professionals are required to reform their practice with more innovative approaches and inclusive environments acknowledging diverse identities (Rhodes & Coda, 2017).

There are limited studies that examine the lived experiences of English language teachers while implementing the MATATAG Curriculum. Much of what has been studied to date remains policy-level analysis or general curriculum content without discussing how teachers perceive and navigate the challenges of implementation within their classroom contexts (Liang, 2021; Ferdaus & Novita, 2023). This study addresses this gap by situating teachers' voices and presenting qualitative insights that are too frequently absent from larger, quantitative measures of curriculum change.

This study is anchored to Jack Mezirow's (1970) Transformative Learning Theory and Michael Fullan's (1982) Change Theory. Mezirow's (1970) theory explains how individuals change their points of view by critically examining experience. English teachers can experience transformative learning as they adjust to new classroom practices, content, and teaching approaches. On the other hand, Fullan's (1982) theory describes how individuals and institutions react to education reforms. English teachers' experiences can be viewed through this theory, particularly as they cope with training, availability of resources, and changing expectations under the MATATAG Curriculum.

Furthermore, a few literature have examined the effectiveness and availability of support mechanisms in the teaching of English. The absence of data-driven intervention on the needs of teachers is a focus for this research. Hence, this study explored the lived experiences of junior high school English language teachers regarding the pilot implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum, which was the basis for the development plan.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework consists of three main components: Input, Process, and Output.

Figure 1

Paradigm of the Study

The input section involves the experiences, obstacles, support systems and resources, and strategies employed by the English teachers in classrooms. The Process section outlines the methodology applied. Purposive sampling was applied to gather data, targeting English teachers who directly participated in executing MATATAG. This research was treated qualitatively, where interviews and focus group discussions (FGD) were conducted and analyzed with coding and thematic analysis. Moreover, the

Output section is a Proposed Development Plan to address the problems and gaps encountered in the MATATAG curriculum implementation process.

Research Objectives

This study explored the lived experiences of junior high school English language teachers regarding implementing the MATATAG Curriculum at the Schools Division of Bataan S.Y. 2024-2025, which was the basis for crafting the development plan. Specifically, this study was conducted to explore the experiences of English language teachers, to identify their obstacles, to determine the extent of the support system and resources they have, and to describe strategies and approaches they employ during the implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum to propose a development plan.

Methodology

This research used a phenomenological study as the qualitative methodology to explore English teachers' experiences, obstacles, received support, and strategies in the pilot implementation of the MATATAG curriculum. The Schools Division of Bataan was used as this locale has already implemented the MATATAG curriculum in the schools. A purposive sampling technique was used to determine the samples. The selected teacher respondents handled Grade 7 English classes in the junior high schools at the Schools Division of Bataan. This grade level was chosen, as the pilot implementation of the new curriculum is among the Grade 7. Also, teacher participants were teaching for over three years to understand the previous and new curriculums.

Further, ten (10) participants were used as a sample size. This number was enough to follow the principle of data saturation, where these participants could

generate in-depth views about the English language teachers' experiences in implementing the MATATAG curriculum.

The DepEd Order No. 16 s. 2017 is utilized under the DepEd Research Management Guidelines to formally request permission to conduct the study at the Division of Bataan. A request letter to conduct the study was delivered to the Superintendent of the Schools Division of Bataan, where the methodology was also attached to ensure that the office was informed about the relevant information about the study. This document was essential to show that the proposed study would fall according to the standard scope of the DepEd concerning conducting research.

After securing the permit from the Schools Division Office, the researcher asked for consent from the senior high school principals. Their consent allowed the researcher to gather relevant data among the language teachers in their schools. Then, the teachers were given informed consent to participate in the study. They were informed about the study procedures and objectives and notified about their rights as respondents.

Additionally, semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions (FGD) were used to gather qualitative data. Open-ended questions to gather data were utilized about English teachers' experiences, challenges, perceptions of provisions like support and resources, and practical strategies to address the demands in the MATATAG Curriculum. These instruments provided a better understanding of the participants' experiences.

Furthermore, the present undertaking utilized thematic analysis to analyze the transcribed data from the FGDs and interviews. The coding of this study adhered to Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis framework. It began with the researchers' familiarization with the focus group discussions and interviews that had been transcribed. Open coding followed, whereby specific codes were assigned to

meaningful text units that reflected particular ideas, experiences, or sentiments expressed by English language teachers. The codes summarized surface meanings and insights, and similar codes were grouped into more general categories so that the data could be organized into meaningful patterns.

These themes were then analyzed and synthesized. The researcher then verified each theme against the raw data, and the problems were understood within the literature and relevant theories.

Below were the sample interview questions used in the study:

Part 1 Teachers' Experiences: How would you explain your experience with the MATATAG Curriculum? How was it different from the curricula previously taught?

Part 2 Teachers' Challenges: What are the significant challenges you encounter in the implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum, and how do they influence your daily teaching?

Part 3 Teachers' Support and Resources: How would you measure the support given by the school administration for the MATATAG Curriculum? Are there some areas where you need more support?

Part 4 Teachers' Strategies and Techniques: Have any methods or methodologies that you used to achieve what the MATATAG Curriculum tries to accomplish?

Results (Findings)

The table below shows the language teacher's experiences implementing the MATATAG Curriculum.

Table 1

Experiences of Language Teachers in MATATAG Curriculum

Codes	Categories	Themes	Descriptions
R3: "There are many adjustments, and I need to study or look for further ways." R5: "Adapting to the new framework required significant adjustments." R8: "It is tiring."	Teacher Adjustments	Overwhelming new topics, significant adjustments, fatigue	The MATATAG curriculum implementation results in significant changes and adjustments among language educators.
R1: "Examples here are all about Philippine and Southeast Asian culture..." R6: "Students are exposed to Philippine literary works." R7: "Lessons are contextualized for cultural appreciation and relevance."	Localized and Contextualized Content	Focus on Philippine culture and contextualized examples	The content focuses on the Philippines and other Southeast Asia countries' cultural lessons.
R2: "The focus on foundational skills boosts my students' engagement and learning." R5: "Essential competencies equip students with real-life applications." R7: "Students gain confidence and foundational skills."	Foundational Skill Development	Emphasis on foundational competencies and life skills	Language teachers highlight the essential life skills and competencies that students need to boost their confidence and engagement.
R2: "Students have responded positively... showing improved focus and enthusiasm." R7: "Students seem more engaged, especially with its relatable content." R6: "Students participate actively in contextualized learning activities."	Positive Engagement	Positive engagement with contextualized activities	The new curriculum requires the teachers to be creative in providing contextualized activities that promote student engagement in the lessons.

The MATATAG curriculum implementation resulted in significant changes and adjustments among language teachers through adapting to new topics, innovating teaching approaches, or dealing with exhaustion. The teacher respondents described the new curriculum as tiring and demanding, as it was overwhelming and required additional work and effort.

One strength of the new curriculum was the emphasis on contextualized and localized content that focused on the cultural lessons of the local and other Southeast Asian countries. Language teachers maximized literary works and valuable materials to foster practical learning experiences and allowed the students to establish their identity as part of the specific culture.

In addition, implementing the MATATAG curriculum focused on the students' development of basic skills and competencies to boost their confidence and engagement. The new curriculum required language teachers to be creative. They

needed to provide contextualized activities that promote student enthusiasm in the lesson (Merueña, 2023).

The table below depicts the challenges encountered by the language teacher in implementing the MATATAG Curriculum.

Table 2
Challenges of the Language Teachers in MATATAG Curriculum

Codes	Categories	Themes	Descriptions
R1: "It has insufficient details, so you need to search for additional information online." R4: "Lack of learning materials."	Resource and Knowledge Gaps	Lack of Instructional Materials	The language teachers struggled in the lack of provided instructional materials which are necessary to support the learning.
R4: "Students have zero knowledge of the foundation of the learning area." R5: "The students also do not have the foundational knowledge needed for the topics." R6: "Poor writing output of the students."		Student Knowledge Gaps	Teachers observed the lack of basic knowledge among students.
R2: "I have to juggle time constraints due to the overwhelming competencies to be achieved per quarter." R3: "Congested topics and overwhelming activities... The curriculum is new, and they allotted us 45 to 50 minutes only to teach the lesson." R5: "Too many topics to teach but limited time."	Overwhelming Curriculum Demands	Excessive Competencies to Cover	The limited timeframe was not sufficient to effectively deliver the congested topics and activities.
R3: "I have extra time to think of some ways to extract the most essential lessons." R7: "Preparing contextualized materials has increased my workload."	Impact on Teacher Workload	Additional Time for Planning	Teachers expressed that their workload had increased.

Language teachers faced numerous obstacles and challenges during the pilot implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum. They struggled with lacking instructional materials to support learning. Hence, language teachers became resilient in searching online materials to solve these problems. Also, teachers observed the lack of basic knowledge among students as it was difficult for the students to cope with the lessons as they did not master the foundational knowledge relevant to learning more complicated concepts and lessons. Grade 7 students were struggling with poor writing skills and possessed very beginner status in particular lessons.

Other challenges were the limited timeframe and the significant impact on workloads. Language teachers only have 45 minutes per class, that was insufficient to cover the curriculum demands, and they spend additional time designing and planning lessons, specifically determining the essential lessons and adapting and preparing contextualized learning aids and activities (Garma, 2024).

The table below describes the provided support during the implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum.

Table 3

Provided Support on the MATATAG Curriculum

Codes	Categories	Themes	Descriptions
R6: "No books provided, no readymade PowerPoint presentations of the lessons." R4: "They should also initiate the provision of materials, especially for the learners." R3: "I have to print my learners' activity sheets and materials for the smooth teaching-learning process."	Limited Administrative Support	Lack of Ready-Made Materials	Teachers expressed frustration over the absence of essential resources.
R7: "The professional development sessions have helped introduce the core principles of the MATATAG Curriculum, but they have been somewhat brief." R2: "Training sessions made me realize what our education system lacks." R5: "No. The training should also consider the availability of resources. Almost all of the subjects lack the necessary materials."	Need for Professional Development	Insufficient Depth of Training	Teachers lacked the necessary skills and resources.

Limited administrative support occurred because the classes lacked readymade learning materials. Essential resources such as books and PPT presentations were not available. Hence, teachers had no choice but to provide for themselves, particularly by printing their learner's activity sheets and materials that add to their workload.

In addition, the provision of needed professional development for the new curriculum was lacking among the language teachers. Though the limited training sessions introduced the principles of the new curriculum, these sessions were too brief and shallow to address the gaps and complexities adequately. The current curriculum

fell short of equipping the language teachers with the needed resources and skills to successfully implement it among the learners (Lagbao, 2024).

The table below manifests the language teacher's strategies when implementing the MATATAG Curriculum.

Table 4
Strategies Employed on the MATATAG Curriculum

Codes	Themes	Codes	Descriptions
R1: "Venn diagram, hands on activities"	Effective Strategies for Meeting Objectives	Visual and Organizational Tools	Use of visual aids to structure learning.
R2: "Building an online classroom such as Google Classroom caters to my needs in identifying learners' improvement in writing as well as their inevitable use of AI apps in answering their activities."		Technology Integration	Building online classrooms, leveraging AI applications and interactive tools.
R3: "Since it is congested, I have to unpack the lessons and make it easier for the suitability and capacity of my learners."		Simplification and Adaptation	Unpacking and simplifying lessons to make them suitable for diverse learners.
R2: "I construct activities relatable to their everyday life."	Adapting Teaching Methods to Student Diversity	Relatable Content	Designing lessons that are relevant to students' lives.
R3: "I may choose the activities that best suit my learners, and I can modify the lessons for the effectiveness of my teaching since I know my learners."		Learner-Centered Methods	Personalizing activities by considering learners' unique needs.
R4: "Collaborative activities" R7: "Project-based learning and collaborative group activities have been particularly effective in engaging students. They are helpful for the students to apply concepts in real-world contexts. I use formative quizzes, online tools, and reflective journals."	Helpful Activities, Assessments, and Resources	Collaborative and Engaging Activities	Group work and project-based learning to foster student engagement.
R5: "The provided worksheets and lesson plans are helpful."		Standardized Materials	Using DepEd-provided worksheets and lesson plans.
R4: "Collaboration through open communication is a big help."	Adaptability	Peer Collaboration and Support	Engaging in collaborative sessions with colleagues.

Language teachers focused on attaining the lesson objectives, adapting the pedagogical methods, and providing meaningful activities. Visuals and organizational tools helped simplify complicated concepts and aid the students in learning the lesson easily. In addition, technology integration innovated learning by tracking students' progress and improving their engagement. Google Classroom and artificial intelligence (AI) were useful platforms for employing the new curriculum.

Language teachers designed relevant and engaging lessons and provided activities. Also, respondents shared the necessity of administering assessments to monitor students' language needs and improvement. Digital tools were also helpful for innovating instruction. They could make the language teaching-learning process more interactive, which lets the students focus and be engaged. Nevertheless, the table showed that the department's standardized resources were useful as their contents aligned with the expected competencies and objectives. However, it would be much better if the department provided additional resources like books and visuals (Estrellado, 2024).

Further, language teachers value the contribution of peer collaboration and support systems. Peer sharing provided them with problem-solving opportunities through open communication. The table below presents the crafted development plan to address the challenges encountered by language teachers during the implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum.

Table 5

Development Plan for the MATATAG Curriculum

Key Areas	Action Steps	Expected Outcome
Professional Development and Capacity Building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Conduct comprehensive, in-depth training focusing on practical strategies, localized content integration, and foundational skill development. b. Offer workshops on managing time-constrained lessons and prioritizing key competencies. c. Organize skill-specific training for addressing students' knowledge gaps, such as remedial writing and foundational literacy skills. d. Provide training on the effective use of educational technology. 	Teachers become confident and well-equipped to implement the curriculum efficiently and address student needs effectively.
Administrative and Resource Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Design and develop contextualized resources and distribute sufficient books needed for instruction. b. Provide schools with a repository of digital resources c. Allocate funds or support for printing student activity sheets and other essential materials. d. Extend lesson durations where feasible to allow for in-depth discussion of competencies. 	Reduced workload for teachers to focus on teaching and less on resource preparation.

Curriculum Adaptation and Streamlining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Review and adjust the curriculum by identifying overlapping or non-essential topics. b. Focus on manageable core competencies per lesson. c. Integrate real-life applications and project-based assessments to consolidate learning outcomes. 	A streamlined curriculum that is practical, focused, and achievable within the allocated lesson time.
Peer Collaboration and Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Establish professional learning communities (PLCs) for sharing best practices, lesson plans, and innovative teaching strategies. b. Facilitate regular peer mentoring sessions. c. Encourage open forums or group chats for ongoing communication and support. 	A supportive community of educators working collaboratively to address challenges and sustain motivation.
Teacher Well-Being and Resilience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Provide mental health support programs to help teachers manage stress and fatigue. b. Encourage time management and work-life balance through practical strategies and tools. c. Recognize and reward teachers' efforts and innovations in implementing the curriculum. 	Improved teacher morale and well-being, leading to greater instructional resilience and productivity.
Student Engagement and Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Design interventions to address foundational knowledge gaps among students, such as remedial classes or peer tutoring programs. b. Develop engaging, culturally relevant activities to foster active participation and enthusiasm for learning. c. Incorporate formative assessments to monitor and address student progress continuously. 	Enhanced student engagement and improved learning outcomes, aligned with the curriculum's goals.

This development plan aims to improve administrative support and teacher professional development to address the gaps faced by language teachers, promote innovative and collaborative approaches that integrate localized and contextualized content for more meaningful learning, and ensure teachers' well-being.

Language teachers needed sustained and comprehensive professional development to improve curriculum implementation. Training programs must dig deep and give importance to practical strategies to address the gaps in the curriculum. Workshops and training must include methods for integrating contextualized content and basic skills while observing a time-bound instruction. Language teachers must have sufficient techniques to deal with foundational gaps, such as remedial instructions and technology integration. Digital tools such as Google Classroom and AI applications must also be included in the training to innovate instruction. These educational technologies help track students' progress and design interactive lessons. The development initiatives would empower the language teachers to effectively implement

the MATATAG curriculum among the students by equipping the language teachers with the needed skills, strategies, and tools (Saro et al., 2024).

Insufficient resources were a common challenge for language teachers. Consequently, the schools and administrators must provide essential teaching materials like books, presentations, and worksheets aligned with the competencies and objectives incorporated in the new curriculum. Digital repositories could be useful for providing accessible tools to language teachers. Moreover, schools must allocate enough funds to give or print important materials like the student's activity sheets. The extension of instruction time must also be considered to cover the needed competencies in the new curriculum among the students among the students. These initiatives are important to lighten the burden and workload of the language teachers so that they can focus primarily on instruction.

Nevertheless, the MATATAG curriculum must be further studied and reviewed. The strengths must be identified, and the non-essential topics must be reduced. The competencies must be measured and aligned to the student's level, and equality in the depth and breadth of the instruction must be observed. Also, integrating real-life context and project-based assessments must be time-bound to guarantee that the lessons are achievable and practical. This enables teachers to focus on meaningful teaching while not becoming pressured into covering excessive topics.

Further, peer collaboration and support networks are significant for fostering a shared purpose and sense of community that benefits language teachers. Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) will allow educators to share helpful practices, innovative strategies, and updated materials. Regular peer mentoring and forums can be a great solution to address gaps and common problems by having open communication that invites a supportive and collaborative environment.

Teachers noted that implementing the new curriculum brings fatigue and exhaustion through its complicated demands. Hence, teachers must be prioritized by developing mental health programs to maintain a healthy lifestyle. They must be given approaches to handle workloads effectively by equipping them with stress and time management strategies.

For student engagement and support, teachers must incorporate culturally relevant lessons and activities that reflect the students' lives. This will create an active and participative learning environment as the students can relate to the lessons (Villaver et al., 2024). Moreover, formative assessments like journals, quizzes, and other paper and pen activities must be provided to reinforce learning and address knowledge gaps. Additionally, investigations into the workload and well-being of educators during curriculum transitions inform strategies for improving teacher support. This intervention must be employed in different timelines or phases. In the short term, its implementation will range from 0 to 6 months, and the development and provision of the necessary resources and training sessions must be done. In the medium term, ranging from 6 to 12 months, peer collaboration and implementation monitoring must be checked to determine the impact of the adjustments and the other things to improve. In the long term, the overall aspect and effectiveness of the intervention must be assessed and refined.

Regular monitoring and evaluation will significantly determine the program's success in the development plan. Students' performances must also be assessed to determine the curriculum's impact.

Discussions

English Teachers' Experiences

MATATAG Curriculum brought positive and negative adjustments and changes among English language teachers as they experienced exhaustion and challenges, exposing the physical and psychological issues to adopt a more demanding and contextualized learning approach. Despite the challenges, most of the teachers appreciated the emphasis of the curriculum on localized and culturally contextualized content, which allowed them to use Philippine and Southeast Asian literature as a reference point for teaching. Although the curriculum introduces more work and pressure, it also results in more meaningful and appropriate education. While the curriculum is promising in content, its sustainability depends on how much teachers are facilitated along its transitions. These findings assume that addressing the workload and emotional demands of teachers is critical to ensuring effective implementation and maintaining teaching quality (Malinao & Miano, 2025).

Challenges Encountered

Some of the significant issues encountered by English teachers were insufficient instructional material, lack of prior knowledge of the students, congested lesson content, and insufficient instructional time (Osias et al., 2024). Teachers reported that Grade 7 students had "zero knowledge" in some topics; thus, it was challenging to cope with the desired learning competencies. Classes only had 45 minutes, which was not adequate for the lessons, and teachers spent additional time contextualizing materials, affecting instruction and personal lives. These concerns indicate a mismatch between the curriculum expectations and classroom realities. Unless student foundation gaps are filled and teacher workloads are alleviated through systemic support, the impact of the curriculum on the teaching-learning process will be challenging (Garma, 2024).

Support System and Resources

The MATATAG Curriculum implementation was hampered by inadequate support systems, primarily in administrative support and professional growth. Teachers were disappointed with the lack of fundamental teaching materials like textbooks and pre-prepared lesson presentations. Teachers had to make their own, taking away their time and effort from actual teaching. Professional growth activities provided were usually too short to train the teachers comprehensively for the new curriculum. These findings expressed a pressing necessity for more practice-oriented and resource-conscious training events that mirror actual classroom needs (Lagbao, 2024). The implication is that in order for curriculum change to be achieved, there should be firm managerial backing and adequate quality teacher education as a prerequisite so teachers will feel inspired and not deterred by innovation (Demate et al., 2025).

Strategies and Approaches

English teachers employed various strategies like employing visual organizers, integrating technology (e.g., Google Classroom and AI tools), and minimizing content. They also use student-centered approaches like project-based learning and remediation. Activities were contextualized to engage the students. Peer support and emotional support also emerged as potent coping mechanisms. These findings show that these coping mechanisms reflect teachers' determination and resilience against deficits in the institution. They show innovations in the cause of learning (Uy et al., 2024). However, if the curriculum would be implemented in the long term, the mechanisms must be backed institutionally. The implication is that best practices could serve as a model for school policy and training program development (Gulmayo & Subillaga, 2025).

Proposed Development Plan

The proposed development plan addresses both the pedagogical and structural issues, emphasizing professional development, curriculum rationalization, resource

provision, peer support, the well-being of teachers, and student welfare. Also, the plan focuses on building teacher capacity, curriculum rationalization, and bridging learning gaps among students. It is a long-term measure, not only enhances the process of instruction and learning in the short term but also contributes to the sustainability of the MATATAG Curriculum change in the long run. Ultimately, it builds a more equitable and compassionate system of education in which both the teachers and students can thrive (Labag, 2025).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The main goal of this research was to explore the experiences, difficulties, and practices of English language teachers in implementing the MATATAG Curriculum. The study findings contribute an essential fill to the gaps of the new curriculum by providing empirical investigation of how teachers perceive and are affected by the changes in the curriculum.

English Teachers' Experiences. While teachers appreciate the nature of the MATATAG Curriculum, they are also exhausted by the additional workload of implementation. These were theoretically contributory to the Change Theory, where the voice of teachers was highlighted in building the curriculum. It also supports the Transformative Learning Theory, affirming that teaching contexts play a significant role in the teaching-learning process.

Challenges Encountered. A number of barriers are explored, including the absence of instructional materials, inadequate foundational knowledge among students, overcrowded content, and limited instructional time. These results are consistent with theories of curriculum implementation that emphasize the importance of alignment between curriculum design, teacher capacity, and institutional support. Jack Mezirow's

(1970) Transformative Learning Theory and Michael Fullan's (1982) Change Theory hold that without proper structural and emotional support, education will not be successful.

Support System. Teachers lacked proper administrative support and professional development. This is a denial of capacity-building framework principles, which assume that teacher change depends on continuous learning and empowering teachers. Support systems should be institutional, not temporary, and professional development should be contextual and longitudinal.

The study concludes that while the MATATAG Curriculum is theoretically sound, its implementation is constrained by systemic conditions such as insufficient support, material constraints, and teacher work overload. The study has implications for education theories advocating participatory curriculum development and teacher autonomy. Practically, this study appeals to the Department of Education to invest in continuous professional development, reduce curriculum content complexity, and produce ready-to-use materials. Policy-wise, it calls for reconsideration of instruction time, workload for teachers, and alignment of curriculum with the readiness levels of students.

Further, one of the drawbacks of this study is its focus on a narrow sample of teachers from focused pilot schools, and this can limit the generalizability of findings. Second, the data received were reliant to a large degree on self-reporting, and this may have been susceptible to bias. The path ahead would be to have bigger samples along with student, school principal, and curriculum planner voices for more insight into the implementation context.

Future research can prioritize longitudinal studies to establish the long-term effect of the MATATAG Curriculum on teacher practice and student learning

outcomes. Investigating the efficacy of specific teaching approaches and teacher professional development programs in the context of MATATAG can yield more actionable recommendations. Quantitative research on student achievement and teacher satisfaction measures over time can also complement current findings and offer more concrete bases for policymaking on the curriculum.

Statements and Declarations

1. Funding details. This work relies only on the author's interest, so no funding is to be declared. It is independent research that drives the author to explore the problem of the current trend in education, particularly the implementation of the new curriculum.

2. Disclosure statement. This work observes high integrity, and ethical considerations ensure that the data are evaluated and analyzed. The respondents participate voluntarily, and the citations and references are acknowledged appropriately.

3. Acknowledgement: The researcher is grateful to the Schools Division of Bataan participants for their support in conducting this study.

4. Ethical Approval: To ensure integrity, ethical considerations are applied by having peer reviewers validate and assess the instrument, data, and analysis.

5. Declaration of Generative AI in Scientific Writing: The author wrote this study with a limited AI index to declare. Generative Artificial intelligence (AI) tools are utilized to back up the analyses and interpretations of the data to ensure its accuracy and to enhance readability and language during the writing of this research.

Authorship and Citation: The author declares that this study is an original work that observes integrity and academic rigor. All references, sources, and ideas in this research are properly cited and acknowledged to avoid plagiarism and adhere to the ethical conduct of this study.

Disclosure Instructions: During the preparation of this work, the author used Gemini and PaperPal to validate the analysis and interpretations of the data and to quickly search for possible literature needed in the study. After using these AI-assisted technologies, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the publication's content.

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